

EVALUATION OF DISTINCT THERMAL MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN ELECTRIC VEHICLE BATTERY PACKS

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Abstract: The effects of global warming on the climate becomes more evident each year. Approximately 20% of the emitted CO₂ is due to transportation. Therefore, many countries took action to minimize their effect on the environment by accelerating transition to electric vehicles via tax deduction and bans of internal combustion engines. Most of the components in electric vehicles such as electric motor, inverter and control system are well known and satisfy the requirements for advanced vehicles. However, battery technology limits the advancement. Literature focus on the battery chemistry to maximize energy and power density. Publications show that battery life and performance can be enhanced if battery cell temperature is kept at the desired operation temperature which is around 30°C. In addition, if the temperature exceeds a limit temperature short circuit is triggered due to melted separator, Lithium dendrite growth and/or decreased electric resistance in the cell. Thermal management of battery cells is essential due to these reasons. Furthermore, heat generation rate in cells is not easily predictable and constant as in electronic components. Depending on the charging (or discharging) rate and state of charge (or depth of discharge) heat generation rate varies and it is non-homogeneous. Furthermore, battery cells required to be heated in some ambient conditions. There are many distinct strategies for thermal management of electric vehicle battery packs such as air cooling, liquid cooling, phase changing materials (PCMs) and immersion in dielectric liquid bath in the literature. This paper compares the distinct strategies for various use cases and documents their advantages as well as disadvantages. In addition to the removal of the generated heat, required weight and space allocations also considered as these are important parameters is commercial electric vehicles in the market. The results show that there is no strategy perfect for all the use cases, and that the strategy should be decided based on battery chemistry, ambient conditions, operation conditions and constraint related with the vehicle design such as weight and volume.

Keywords: Battery thermal management, Heat transfer enhancement, Air cooling, Liquid cooling, Phase changing materials, Immersion cooling.

Özet: Her geçen yıl küresel ısınmalarının iklim üzerinde etkileri daha görünür olmaktadır. Salınan CO₂'nin yaklaşık %20'si taşımacılıktandır. Bu nedenle birçok ülke çevreye olan etkiyi en düşük seviyeye çekmek için elektrikli araçlara geçişi vergi indirimleri ve içten yanmalı motorları yasaklayarak hızlandırmaktadır. Elektrikli araçların elektrik motoru, invertör ve kontrol sistemi gibi birçok bileşeni gelişmiş araçlar için gerekli şartları sağlamaktadır. Ancak, batarya teknolojisi gelişmeyi sınırlamaktadır. Literatür enerji ve güç yoğunluğunu en yüksek seviyeye çekmek için batarya kimyasına odaklanmaktadır. Yayınlar batarya ömrü ve performansının batarya hücre sıcaklığının 30°C civarında istenen sıcaklık değerinde tutulduğunda artırılabileceğini göstermektedir. Ek olarak, sınır sıcaklık değerinin geçilmesi durumunda eriyen separatör, Lityum dendrit büyümesi ve/veya batarya içinde azalan elektrik direnç nedeniyle kısa devre tetiklenir. Bu nedenlerden dolayı batarya hücrelerinin ısı yönetimi önem arz etmektedir. İlaveten, bataryaların ısı üretim oranı elektronik bileşenlerde olduğu gibi kolay tahmin edilebilir ve sabit değildir. Şarj (deşarj) oranına ve şarj (deşarj) oranına bağlı olarak ısı üretim oranı değişir ve homojen değildir. Ek olarak, batarya hücrelerinin bazı ortam koşullarında ısıtılması gerekmektedir. Literatürde elektrikli araç batarya paketlerinin ısı yönetimi için hava soğutma, sıvı soğutma, faz değiştiren malzemeler (FDM) ve dielektrik sıvı banyosuna daldırma gibi birçok farklı strateji bulunmaktadır. Bu makale farklı çalışma koşulları için farklı stratejileri kıyaslar ve onların avantajları ile dezavantajlarını dökümantate etmektedir. Ticari elektrikli araç piyasasında önemli parametreler olduğu için gerekli ağırlık ve hacim ihtiyacı, üretilen ısının uzaklaştırılmasına ek olarak değerlendirilmiştir. Sonuçlar, tüm şartların için en iyi sonucu verecek bir strateji olmadığını, ve stratejinin batarya kimyası, ortam koşulları, çalışma koşulları ve ağırlık ile hacim gibi araç tasarım kısıtlarına göre karar verilmesi gerektiğini göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Batarya ısı yönetimi, Isı transfer artırımı, Hava soğutma, Sıvı soğutma, Faz değiştiren malzemeler, Daldırma soğutma.

INTRODUCTION

Global warming and climate change requires actions to be taken toward diminishing their effect on daily life, and one of them is minimizing harmful emissions related with transportation. Electric vehicles will be replacing internal combustion cars due to their low affect on the environment especially if the electricity source is renewable such as solar and wind. They are also a lot more efficient; for instance, energy conversion efficiency is a lot greater in batteries (electrochemical to electricity); therefore, stored energy can be converted into motion with more than 80% efficiency in electric car which is around 20-40% in internal combustion counterparts [Roschner et al., 2013]. However, this transition is possible only if the energy and power density of battery cells increases to the level which satisfies the requirements of the electric vehicle market. [Foley and Olabi, 2017]. Research on novel battery cell chemistries is an ongoing subject to enhance battery cell energy and power density with increased lifetime. However, majority agrees on Li-ion battery cells is suitable for the current applications and they would dominate for the next decade at least due to their high energy density and lack of memory effect [Kim et al., 2019]. In addition, Li-ion batteries could vary depending on their electrode material where some of the electrode materials are Lithium Manganese Oxide, Lithium Titanate Oxide, Lithium Cobalt Oxide, Lithium Iron Phosphate, Lithium Nickel Manganese Cobalt Oxide and Lithium Nickel Cobalt Aluminum Oxide [Gungor et al., 2021]. Even though there are many distinct electrode materials, the temperature range in which the efficiency becomes the maximum vary in between 15°C and 35°C for all Li-ion batteries [Pesaran and Santhanagopalan, 2013]. If the temperature is lower than this range cell internal resistance increases and above the lifetime decreases due to degradation. Therefore, battery cells are required to be held in this temperature range, i.e. heating is required as well as cooling.

In addition to the conversion efficiency and lifetime of cells heavily depend on temperature, safe operation requires operation temperature stay under the maximum temperature limit to avoid thermal runaway [Feng et al., 2019]. Thermal runaway occurs due to short circuit which may be triggered due to the melting of separator which happens at elevated temperatures as cell internal resistance decreases. Furthermore, other reasons are related with dissolving of materials due to lower voltage level than cut-off voltage or mechanical damage such as punctured separator. Separator can also be damaged due to the formation of Lithium dendrites. Literature shows that the Lithium dendrite formation is affected by the cell temperature [Gao et al., 2020]. Therefore, safe operation of Li-ion batteries requires temperature to be kept under a limit value as well as controlling maximum and minimum voltage level.

Battery cells can be charged/discharged with a given speed based on their chemistry and this speed is called

C-rate which is 1 if the battery is charged/discharged in an hour. If C-rate is 2 then charging/discharging occurs in thirty-minutes. C-rate is an essential parameter as it is useful to document current flowing in the system based on the capacity of battery cell. Heat generation is therefore function of C-rate as well as being non-homogeneous and time dependent due to its nature [Schuster et. al., 2015; Panchal et. al., 2016; Neupane et. al., 2018; Xie et. al., 2020]. Transferring the generated heat from the battery pack is essential to keep the pack temperature in the desired operational range. Requirements of advanced electric vehicles such as fast and ultra-fast charging are keep increasing the volumetric heat generation rate. However, throughout the charging/discharging cycle of battery cells heat generation vary greatly with C-rate as well as the charge level of battery, state of charge (SoC) or depth of discharge (DoD). Therefore, heat generation rate varies several folds in each cyclic operation. Therefore, a thermal management system with variable heating/cooling load becomes the necessity. There are many distinct heat transfer mechanisms in the literature for the thermal management of electric vehicles such as air cooling [Li et. al., 2019; Akinlabi and Solyali, 2020; Gocmen et. al., 2020], liquid cooling [Panchal et. al., 2017, Huang et. al., 2019, Xu et. al., 2020], immersion cooling [Patil et. al., 2021] and thermal management with phase changing materials [Xie et. al., 2017; Jaguemont et. al., 2018; Celik et. al., 2019; Joshy et. al., 2020].

Electric vehicles will need to perform their tasks in distinct locations as they will keep replacing the internal combustion vehicles. This would mean the ambient temperatures would vary in between extreme temperatures. For example, temperature would drop to minus 20°C in the continental Europe during winter as it would go up to 50°C in continental Africa. Therefore, the effect of ambient temperature should be considered during the evaluation of how the thermal managements should be. The current literature is lacking because there is no discussion on the effect of ambient temperature for distinct heat transfer mechanisms. Furthermore, size and weight restrictions in the car market is also being overlooked in the publications with the interest of thermal management system development. This paper aims to uncover advantages and disadvantages of each thermal management strategy with the consideration of ambient temperature and market requirements. Therefore, the energy requirement for distinct ambient conditions is discussed in addition to the increment in the volume and weight for distinct strategies. The results show that phase changing materials and immersion cooling with dielectric fluids become advantageous if the ambient temperature is in the range of optimum operational temperature range. They become the worst options as the difference in between the ambient temperature and operation temperature increases.

Battery Thermal Management Strategies

There are many distinct thermal management strategies, and some of them are being used in electric vehicles and others are still in the development phase. Air and liquid cooling with or without combining a vapor compression cycle is the trend in current electric vehicles. There are many reasons for that, and one of them is that the knowledge on air and liquid cooling in car manufacturers. Some examples with liquid cooling structure are Audi e-Tron, Mercedes EQC, Tesla Model S, Jaguar I-Pace, Hyundai Kona, Tesla Model 3. Renault ZOE ZE50, Nissan Leaf, VW e-Golf and Skoda CITIGO-e iV can be given as examples to the air cooled vehicles. Furthermore, there are many articles in the literature documenting thermal management with air and liquid cooling.

In addition, there are some strategies still in the phase of development to be used in palpable electric vehicles which are immersion cooling, phase changing materials (PCMs), heat pipes and thermo-electric. Heat pipes would not be discussed in this paper because they require excessive volume and weight increases to the unnecessary levels, i.e. volumetric heat generation in a battery pack is relatively smaller in comparison to electronics cooling. Overall, heat pipes is essential for cooling of electronics but in a battery pack which includes at least hundreds of battery cells both weight and cost increases to an unmanageable level. In addition, embedding thermo-electric equipment are not also discussed due to their excessive energy requirement and relatively low energy efficiency. Peltier effect looks promising to supply heating/cooling without any moving parts but decrease in the range becomes in the undesired levels. Therefore, thermo-electric and heat pipes solutions are not considered as they do not conform the requirements of current electric vehicles. They can be applied into battery packs in future if the shortcomings of them are solved. Immersion cooling and PCMs are also have undesirable characteristics but how they are embedded may uncover additional advantages which will be discussed in details in following sections.

Overall, there are competing strategies which are currently being used and being developed. Air, liquid, immersion and PCM heat exchange will therefore be discussed in details.

Air Cooling

Thermal management of battery temperature with air as the working fluid is an attractive solution due to its advantages such as: simple to implement, well known, light weight, low electric conductance, and abundance. In addition, air can be directly sent to the heat generating surfaces without requirement of a heat exchanger. Therefore, the weight required for the thermal management system decreases which is also already low thanks to the low density of air. Figure 1 shows some applications with air cooling for prismatic and cylindrical cells.

Figure 1. (a) Air cooling in a battery pack with U-type flow path [Chen et al., 2017] (b) elevated battery positioning in Z-type flow path for temperature uniformity in battery pack [Gocmen et al., 2020] (c) temperature distribution of square (left) and hexagonal (right) formation of cylindrical battery cells [Wang et al., 2014].

Another advantage of air cooling due to no heat exchanger requirement is actually not that trivial. Because air can be sent directly to the locations where the heat is generated, temperature difference between the hot spot and air is greater than the option to use another working fluid to transfer heat from hot spot and then transferred to air. More specifically, if one considers liquid cooling with a radiator to transfer heat from liquid to air, which is removed from the battery pack. Then, liquid and battery surface should have at least 5°C temperature difference to have a meaningful heat exchange [Incropera et. al, 2007]. In addition, 5°C temperature difference is also required between the working liquid and ambient air. Therefore, approximately 10°C temperature difference is required between the ambient air and battery surface in the existence of a liquid as a carrier of heat. Liquid would be advantageous due to its high capacitance to regulate temperature but only when the ambient air temperature is below a critical limit. Otherwise, the increased operating temperature of liquid would yield an increased cell temperature and using air would become the better option as the temperature difference would be greater, i.e. cell temperature can be kept in the desired order.

However, there are some drawbacks such as low specific heat, variable inlet temperature (ambient temperature), low thermal conductivity. Due to the thermo physical properties of air, achieving temperature uniformity is a difficult task but it is possible if the distribution uniformity is achieved with required mass flow rate is supplied as can be seen in Fig. 1(b) [Gocmen et. al., 2020]. However, air cooling becomes not sufficient if the volumetric heat generation rate increases. Therefore, air cooling would not fit to the applications with relatively high volumetric heat generation such as C-rates being more than 2 especially if SoC/DoD is in a state which could maximize heat generation. In addition, as the thickness/radius of cells increase, heat transfer surface area would decrease and air cooling becomes insufficient as well. Another disadvantage of air cooling is that its temperature vary greatly based on the ambient conditions. Therefore, keeping the temperature of battery cells constant becomes a difficult task as air temperature would vary in a trip based on both location and time of the day. However, please be aware that variation of ambient temperature would not yield operation temperature to exceed safety limit but rather decreases the lifetime of cells due to internal temperature difference or increased internal cell resistance.

Thermo physical properties of air may require the insertion of extended surfaces (fins) into the battery pack to increase heat transfer surface area in between air and battery cells. This would increase the weight of the battery pack. Therefore, it could be considered as a disadvantage. Literature also discusses that if these fins are combined with the battery pack to achieve mechanical support, then, the addition of fins would not change the weight greatly as the mechanical support would already been implemented in some cells such as pouch cells [Gocmen and Cetkin, 2021].

Liquid Cooling

Liquid cooling is a common application for the thermal management of electric vehicle battery packs due to the high capacitance (ρc_p) of liquids which enables the heat to be removed in greater volumetric heat generation rates in comparison to the air counterpart. This is the major advantage of liquid cooling in comparison to the air cooling which also yields enhanced temperature uniformity in battery packs even though the flow uniformity is not in the desired order. However, temperature uniformity could be better but that does not mean it would be satisfying the requirements of keeping the temperature of all the cells in a pack in the desired order. For instance, the wavy channel design of Tesla Company used to form a serpentine heat exchanger in which water-glycol mixture flowing [Adams et al., 2007]. In this design, heat addition from each cell would increase the temperature of mixture along the channel as evident from the 1st law of Thermodynamics cf. Fig. 2. Therefore, there would be temperature non-uniformity but this could be in the acceptable range if the flow rate is adjusted to eliminate the effect of mentioned design.

Figure 2. (a) Tesla battery pack design with serpentine type heat exchanging pipes in which liquid coolant flows [Adams et al., 2007] (b) schematics of it on how temperature of the coolant increases along the pipes.

There are some disadvantages of liquid cooling which are electrical conductance, heat exchanger requirement, leakage, complexity, heavy, corrosive and solidification in low ambient temperatures. Solidification at low temperatures is being solved by mixing an anti-freeze liquid to water such as glycol. However, thermal conductivity is less than the half of the water thermal conductivity. Therefore, the mixture ratio is decided to eliminate solidification and keeping the conductivity of the coolant liquid at the maximum possible. Drawbacks of liquids such as being corrosive and conducting electricity require the usage of heat exchanging surfaces such as cold plates. The cold plates are generally made of Aluminum or Copper and when manifolds, piping, valves, pump, and radiator is added to the system increase in the weight as well as the volume requirement becomes dramatic. The liquid cooling system should not have any leakage as liquid leaking into the battery pack would result in short-circuit. All the required equipment as well as advanced cold plate design makes the liquid cooling system more complex than air cooling.

In addition, an advantage of liquid cooling may become a disadvantage depending on the ambient conditions: high thermal capacitance. In cold environments, as the battery pack of a vehicle is in thermal equilibrium with its ambient, the amount of required energy to heat batteries to the desired order would increase. Because the energy should be supplied is the summation of all components to reach to the desired temperature

$$(m_{bat} C_{bat} + m_{liq} C_{liq} + m_{plate} C_{plate}) \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where m and c are mass and specific heat where subscripts of bat , liq and $plate$ denote battery, liquid coolant and heat exchanger with other components, respectively. Please note that heat leakage to the ambient was not added in Eq. (1).

Immersion Cooling

Thermal management of battery packs with engineered dielectric fluid immersion is a relatively new field. Immersion cooling is being applied in data center thermal management applications which decreases the cost for cooling greatly due to several reason. First advantage of immersion cooling is no need of complex heat exchangers/cold plates as the fluid can directly sweep the surface of heat generating domain. Similar to air cooling application, this would yield enhanced heat exchange as the thermal resistances would decrease. Capacitance of dielectric fluids (cf. Table 1) are lower than liquid water but comparatively greater than air. Therefore, temperature uniformity can be achieved lot easier than air cooling applications. Furthermore, immersion cooling could also conform better temperature uniformity than liquid cooling as heat generating domain is surrounded by dielectric liquid, as can be seen in Fig. 3, unlike cooling from designated surfaces in liquid cooling.

Therefore, no additional heat exchanger is needed in between the dielectric liquid and battery cells which simplifies the design process. However, please be aware a heat exchanger may be needed depending on the application to transfer the generated heat in cells from the battery pack to the ambient. This could be achieved either circulating the dielectric fluid from the pack to a radiator or an additional working fluid can be circulated in a heat exchanger immersed into the dielectric fluid. The rate of heat generated and ambient conditions would uncover whether a heat exchanger would be required or not. Heat exchanger requirement would increase the weight which may decrease the benefit of immersion cooling for thermal management.

Figure 3. Hybrid thermal management (a) battery surface immersed into dielectric fluid and tabs are cooled via forced convection [Patil et al., 2021] and (b) battery module immersed in phase changing liquid (PCL) and coupled with heat pipe radiator [Zhou et al., 2020].

Furthermore, in the case of thermal runaway related with structural deformation propagation would be eliminated. However, there are some essential issues related with this situation. For instance, in order for the battery cells to deform first battery pack should be damaged. Damaged battery pack would not hold dielectric cooling liquid. Therefore, even though in theory thermal runaway propagation would be eliminated with dielectric fluids in the case of accidents, its applicability would be extremely rate, i.e. only top cover of the battery pack would be damaged without any damages on the other surfaces.

Table 1. 3M-Novec 649 (Dodecafluoro-2-methylpentan-3-one) dielectric fluid thermo-physical properties at 25°C [Internet, 2021a].

Density [kg/m ³]	1600
Specific heat [J/kg.K]	1103
Heat of vaporization [kJ/kg]	88
Thermal conductivity [W/m.K]	0.059
Kinematic viscosity [m ² /s]	4×10 ⁻⁷
Dynamic viscosity [Pa.s]	6.4×10 ⁻³
Melting point [°C]	-108
Boiling point [°C]	49
Global warming potential [100 years]	1
Ozone depletion potential	0
Dielectric constant [@1kHz]	1.8
Volume resistivity [Ohm.cm]	10 ¹²

There are also disadvantages of immersion cooling as weight increment is one them. Immersion liquid should fill the battery pack which increases the battery pack

weight greatly. Unlike in liquid cooling not a portion of the volume is filled with coolant but the air gap in the pack is replaced with dielectric liquid. This shows that the weight increment would be more dramatic than the liquid cooling solution. Furthermore, thermal capacitance of the immersion liquid would be high due to the order of mass. This would require additional cooling/heating load if the ambient temperature is hotter or colder than the desired temperature order.

One possible problem is the leakage of the immersion liquid from the battery pack and therefore liquid level should be checked continuously. Leakage could occur not necessarily in liquid phase but also in vapor phase. Boiling point of engineered immersion liquids are generally lower than water and for instance it is 49°C for 3M-Novec 649 as can be seen in Table 1. Latent heat requirement for immersion liquid to boil minimizes the risk of temperature to reach undesired orders. However, increment in the pressure due to phase change would increase the mechanical load in the components located in the battery pack. Therefore, an expansion volume would be required to eliminate any possible problem associated with possible pressure variation. Furthermore, if the ambient temperature is in the order of boiling temperature of the immersion liquid then cooling with vapor-compression cycle becomes essential as vapor thermo physical properties would not conform the required cooling load. Therefore, boiling temperature of the immersion liquid should be considered well based on the ambient conditions in which the vehicle will be used. Some dielectric fluids have even lower boiling point such as in the order of 30°C. For instance, these fluid would not be useful as it may evaporate in an ambient where the temperature exceeding this value even without achieving any cooling at all.

Phase Changing Materials (PCMs)

Another strategy to regulate temperature of a battery pack is embedding phase changing materials into the battery pack. The PCM melts as heat generated in battery cells would be increase the temperature to the melting temperature of it. Then, heat generated in the battery cells does not change the temperature of the pack as heat supplied is stored in latent form. Latent heat of commercial phase changing materials for thermal management applications (phase change temperature would be in the desired operation temperature range) of battery cells would vary around 160–250 kJ/kg [Internet, 2021b]. Therefore, temperature uniformity could be achieved easier as melting occur at constant temperature.

Phase changing material insertion may vary greatly based on the selected material properties. It could be inserted into the pack directly or in enclosures/capsules/porous medium. Direct insertion would yield a simpler design as can be seen in Fig. 4. However, some PCMs are corrosive and may damage the cells. Another reason of why they embedded in enclosures/capsules/porous medium are their relatively low thermal conductivity. During the first minutes of

melting dominant heat transfer mechanism is conduction and then it becomes natural convection. Both are greatly affected from low thermal conductivity values as temperature near the heat generating region can exceed melting temperature without the PCM melts completely [Demirkıran ve Cetkin, 2021]. In order to avoid this situation, PCM can be embedded in enclosures/capsules/porous medium or nano-size solid particles can be distributed into the PCM. These solutions would enhance the thermal conductivity of PCM but electrical conductivity also increases. Therefore, how the PCM distributed in the battery pack should be considered and decided carefully in order to avoid short circuit.

Figure 4. (a) Thermal management of pouch cells with two PCM units [Xie et al., 2017], (b) cylindrical cells surrounded by PCM [Al Hallaj and Selman, 2000] and (c) battery cells covered with PCM with air cooling [Jiang et al., 2017].

Even though the latent heat capacity of PCMs is great (160–250 kJ/kg), additional heat exchanger may be required to cool the system in ambient temperatures greater than the desired operation temperature and in applications with ultra/fast dis/charging in relatively long time span (continuously) cf. Fig. 4c. After PCM melts, temperature would increase dramatically due to relatively low thermal conductivity. This may yield non-uniform temperature distribution in the battery pack and some cell temperatures may exceed the desired operating temperature even though not all the PCM melts.

Another disadvantage of PCMs is due to a phenomenon called sub-cooling. This phenomenon occurs when the liquid PCM temperature decreases to the below of the solidification temperature without the initiation of solidification [Shannaq et al., 2015]. Sub-cooling yields

sensible heat requirement during cooling process and temperature may drop to the undesired values. Sub-cooling is tried to be avoided with chemical additions to avoid sub-cooling to occur during solidification of PCMs.

Furthermore, PCMs may leakage and increment in the pressure due to phase change should also be considered. Liquid specific volumes of PCMs are greater than their solid phase volume. Therefore, volume of PCM increases as it melts. This makes expansion volume as a necessity. Otherwise the system may be damaged due to increased pressure which may reach to great levels due to the incompressible nature of the liquids in the battery pack. Sealing of the pack is essential to avoid leakage of the liquid PCM from battery pack to ambient. Weight increment in the battery pack is another burden of the PCMs.

Use Cases

Battery packs consists of many components in addition to the battery cells. In order to calculate battery pack weight and volume, weight of the cells, bus bars, electrical connections, heat exchanger volume, coolant (dielectric fluid, PCM, etc.), and all the other components as well as container should be summed up. In order to compare distinct solutions, here we adapt a simplified approach. Depending on the cells, cooling solution and materials being used the pack temperature varies from 20% more of the cells to the 50% of the cells. This is a general trend showing the range. Depending on the capacity of the cells, the volume in between the cells decreases; therefore, volume reserved for immersion liquid/PCM actually decreases. Therefore, for the three battery cell configurations considered in here it is adapted that 30, 25 and 20% of additional weight increment applied due to coolant for immersion and PCM cooling options for 18650, 21700 and high energy pouch cells, respectively. It is also considered 25, 20, and 15% weight increment would be necessary for heat exchange surfaces and other components for all the cases air cooling included 18650, 21700 and high energy pouch cells, respectively. Smaller capacity cells would require additional components and yields an increased heat transfer surface area which increased the solid volume. Liquid cooling would require relatively less volume of coolant than immersion and PCM strategies; however, it would require additional heat exchange surfaces and components. Therefore, 5% increment to solid structure and 5% for liquid coolant was added to the weight for the liquid cooling strategy. Three considered cells are Panasonic Sanyo NCR18650GA, Molicel INR21700-P42A and Kokam SLPB130255255G1 as their details can be seen in Table 2. In order to give a general idea, a battery module of 10kW is considered where the voltage and maximum supplied current was not considered. However, it is evident that the maximum supplied voltage is 96V nominal with high energy density Kokam SLPB130255255G1 cells as 26 cells would be sufficient for 10kWh capacity. However, 840 and 660 cells would

be required for the same capacity for Panasonic Sanyo NCR18650GA and Molicel INR21700-P42A cells, respectively. As the number of cells increases so is the freedom to apply for distinct applications. For instance, 26 Serial and 32 Parallel (26S32P) combination of NCR18650GA cells would supply 96 V in nominal and as the number of serial connections increased, the voltage can be varied as current would decrease for the same capacity. Therefore, having many cells with lower capacity actually yields flexibility for configuring battery packs for many distinct cases. However, many cells mean increment in the number of components for connections, spacing, and heat exchanger volume as adapted in the weight increment consideration. Furthermore, specific heat of battery cells, dielectric fluid, PCM, Al and water are 800, 1100, 2000, 900 and 4200 kJ/(kg.K), respectively. These values are average of the considered materials and depending on the materials being used in the battery pack, they should be revised. Here, these average values are adapted to give an order of magnitude idea for the required heat transfer load.

Table 2. Length scale and properties of three distinct battery cells Panasonic Sanyo NCR18650GA, Molicel INR21700-P42A, Kokam SLPB130255255G1 [Internet, 2021c; Internet, 2021d; Internet, 2021e].

NCR18650GA	
Diameter (mm)	18.5
Length (mm)	65.3
Capacity (Ah)	3.3
Nominal Voltage (V)	3.6
Weight (gr)	48
Energy Density (Wh/kg)	280
Max. Current (A)	10
INR21700-P42A	
Diameter (mm)	21.7
Length (mm)	70.2
Capacity (Ah)	4.2
Nominal Voltage (V)	3.6
Weight (gr)	70
Energy Density (Wh/kg)	230
Max. Current (A)	45
SLPB130255255G1	
Width (mm)	268
Length (mm)	265
Thickness (mm)	13.3
Capacity (Ah)	103
Nominal Voltage (V)	3.68
Weight (gr)	1805
Energy Density (Wh/kg)	210
Max. Current (A)	309

Figure 5 shows how the amount of required energy for battery pack to reach 20°C as from the thermal equilibrium state with ambient. The calculations uncover that the amount of energy requirement is maximum with PCM, followed by immersion, liquid and air cooling strategies for all the battery cells. The volume in between the cells decreases as the cell length scale increases; therefore, the difference in between each strategy decreases as size increases. However, that also means that the heat transfer surface area decreases as the size

increases which increases the temperature non-uniformity in the battery pack. Therefore, even though required energy from thermal equilibrium state to operation temperature decreases as the size of the cells increase, achieving the temperature uniformity would be difficult due to limited heat transfer surface area. Therefore, there exists an optimum cell size depending on the cell material properties, optimum temperature and the environment in which it works.

Figure 5. The effect of ambient temperature on the heat transfer energy requirement to reach desired operation temperature from the thermal equilibrium state for PCM, immersion, liquid and air cooling strategies for (a) Panasonic Sanyo NCR18650GA, (b) Molicel INR21700-P42A and (c) Kokam SLPB130255255G1.

Figure 5 also documents that the heat transfer mechanisms do not affect the cooling/heating load if the vehicle operates in between 15 to 35°C. Even though the operation temperature is fixed at 20°C, from 15 to 35°C no additional cooling heating load would be required as the operational range is in that region for Li-ion battery cells. However, please be aware that the volume would be the greatest with air cooling and the weight would be greatest with one of the other solutions

(PCM/immersion/liquid) depending on the design of heat and used coolant.

However, if the ambient temperature reaches to extreme cold and hot values such as below -10 and above 40°C, PCM and immersion cooling solutions would increase the additional heating/cooling load which would decrease the range greatly as witnessed in northern European and African countries. Therefore, ambient temperature should also be considered as the thermal management strategy is being decided as well as other parameters.

CONCLUSIONS

Here it was documented that each battery thermal management strategy has disadvantages as well as advantages, and the proper thermal management strategy should be decided based on the battery cell characteristics (specific heat, thermal conductivity, max. current, heat generation, optimum operation temperature, length scales), ambient conditions and operation characteristics of battery pack. Immersion and PCM are attractive in terms of possibility to achieve uniform temperature distribution in the pack with simple designs. However, they are heavy, leakage and variation in the pressure are their disadvantages. In addition, if the environment temperature is below or above the desired operation temperature, additional heating/cooling load due to the sensible heat requirement for PCM and immersion liquid decreases the range of the vehicle. Liquid cooling also comes with additional cooling/heating load due to capacitance of the heat exchange surfaces and liquid coolant. However, in advanced applications with fast and ultra-fast charging/discharging rates liquid, immersion, or PCM should be implemented as the volumetric heat generation rate cannot be transferred properly with air cooling. However, please be aware the heat transferred from the pack should be transferred to a temperature reservoir (ambient) and therefore PCM, immersion and liquid cooling require additional heat exchange surfaces (heat exchanger, vapor-compression cycle etc.). Even though air cooling has the disadvantage of relatively low thermal capacitance, the weight of air cooled battery packs would be lot smaller than other competitors as well as minimum energy requirement to reach optimum operating temperature from the thermal equilibrium state. Overall, each strategy has its baggage, and combination of these strategies with consideration of minimum energy consumption in distinct use cases as well as minimum possible volume and weight which satisfies the heating/cooling load required for battery cells would be the option rather than implementing them solely.

NOMENCLATURE

ΔT Temperature Difference [°C]
 m Mass [kg]

\dot{m}	Mass Flow Rate [kg/s]
c	Specific Heat [kJ/(kg.K)]
c_p	Specific Heat at Constant Pressure [kJ/(kg.K)]
Q	Heat Transfer Energy [kJ]
\dot{Q}	Heat Transfer Rate [kW]
q	Heat Transfer Rate Dissipated from a Cell [kW]
T	Temperature [°C]

Subscripts

bat	Battery
i, l, n	Index
in	Inlet
liq	Liquid
out	Outlet
plate	Heat Exchanger and Other Components
tot	Total

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